

EDUCATION, LITERACY AND FINANCIAL INCLUSION: OVERCOMING CHALLENGES IN ROMANIA'S FINANCIAL ECOSYSTEM

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Abstract

The article explores the relationship between financial education, financial literacy, and financial inclusion in Romania, aiming to identify ways to improve the effectiveness of financial education programs. It highlights the critical role of financial literacy in promoting economic stability and reducing poverty, especially in the context of a rapidly digitalizing banking sector. The study employs a secondary data analysis methodology, drawing on national reports, academic research, and institutional studies from key financial authorities like the Romanian National Bank and the Ministry of Education. It also assesses the effectiveness of various financial education initiatives targeting different demographic groups, particularly focusing on rural and older populations. Findings indicate that despite increased efforts, Romania faces significant challenges, including low financial literacy rates, a lack of trust in financial institutions, and limited access to financial education in rural areas. Moreover, digital illiteracy further exacerbates financial exclusion, as many are unable to fully utilize digital banking services. This study uniquely examines the role of digital banking as a mediating factor in financial inclusion, particularly for vulnerable groups, while providing a comprehensive evaluation of financial education programs and their effectiveness across different demographic segments in Romania. The article concludes by recommending enhanced collaboration between governmental, financial, and educational institutions to create a more integrated financial education strategy that addresses both literacy and digital skills for improved financial inclusion.

Keywords: *Financial Literacy, Financial Education, Digital Banking, Financial Inclusion, Romania*

INTRODUCTION

Financial education makes a significant contribution to the well-being of the population and thus to economic development. In the European Union, financial education initiatives have gained momentum due to factors such as social exclusion, rising debt, an ageing population, inefficient allocation of resources, declining confidence in financial institutions as a result of the failure of private banks, the 2008 financial crisis and the Swiss franc credit crisis. Efforts have materialized in the development of national financial education strategies, involving intensive collaboration between financial institutions, financial market authorities, educational institutions and the Ministry of Education. Books on financial education written by Romanian authors have appeared, the media is getting

involved in this area and there are financial education programs on radio and TV stations with national coverage.

There are two situations that call into question the real possibilities for increasing financial literacy and financial education. The first aspect is the reluctance of the population, and the second situation that undermines the success of financial education initiatives is the very efficiency and effectiveness of these initiatives, in which case, the opinions of researchers are divergent.

Some research claims that almost half of Romanians rely on their own knowledge or on the advice of friends when making decisions with financial implications and that more than half of Romanians admit that they have not had access to financial information or interest in improving their level of financial education. The lack of trust in financial education and financial institutions is also caused by the numerous events that have marked Romanian society since the Revolution (the three-digit inflation of the 1990s, the devaluation of savings deposited with the CEC, pyramid schemes, private bank bankruptcies, the 2008 crisis, the impact of loans in Swiss francs, the COVID-19 pandemic, the war in Ukraine, etc.).

There are studies demonstrating the usefulness of financial education initiatives but also research questioning their effectiveness. Some researchers argue that financial education programs have a negligible impact on actual financial behaviors, with studies indicating that their effects fade over time. Fernandes et al. (2014) found that financial education efforts explain only 0.1% of the variation in financial behaviors, while Mandell (2011) and Björklund & Sandahl (2023) suggest that financial education alone is insufficient in driving meaningful financial decision-making changes.

In order to increase the effectiveness of financial education initiatives, a number of measures need to be taken to improve the way financial education is taught at secondary and high school level and the way in which teachers who teach this subject are trained. In Romania, a course on "Economic and Financial Education for Teachers" accredited by the Ministry of Education and Research, the National Bank of Romania, the Romanian Banking Association, the Romanian Banking Institute, the Financial Supervisory Authority and the Institute of Financial Studies already exists since 2021.

Even though the responsibility for financial education should lie with the individual, there is a need for collaboration between the state, public institutions with responsibilities in the financial field and private entities active in this sphere in order to implement the Financial Education Strategy and increase financial literacy in Romania.

METHODOLOGY

This study uses a secondary data analysis approach, focusing on existing national reports, academic research, and institutional studies on financial literacy and education in Romania. The data sources include reports from the Romanian National Bank, the Romanian Ministry of Education, and financial institutions that are actively involved in educational initiatives.

The analysis explores existing programs such as the national strategies for financial education and efforts to introduce financial literacy into school curriculums. Additionally, the study examines reports on financial literacy levels, particularly focusing on

populations in rural areas and older generations who may lack access to financial education.

The collected data provide insights into the success and limitations of these initiatives, enabling a comparison of literacy rates and the effectiveness of programs. The study also utilizes qualitative assessments from policy documents and institutional reports to evaluate the institutional efforts in improving financial education.

This approach enables a comprehensive understanding of Romania's current financial education landscape, identifying critical challenges and offering suggestions for enhancing financial literacy efforts across various demographic groups.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Education and development support each other. So do financial education and economic development. Fortunately, in recent years" financial education initiatives have developed rapidly in the European Union, motivated by various international factors such as financial exclusion, ageing population, increasing debt, lack of consumer knowledge or inefficient allocation of public resources" (Nițoi et al. 2022). Romania is among the countries that have developed a Financial Education Strategy and shows other concerns in this respect: "Starting from the 2020-2021 school year, financial education has become a compulsory subject for eighth grade students" (Romanian Government, 2023). Various public (Financial Supervisory Authority, Institute of Financial Studies, National Bank of Romania) and private (commercial banks, insurance companies, various non-profit associations) institutions are developing financial education initiatives. There are several financial education programs on national TV stations and numerous financial publications that the general public can use as sources of information. The Ministry of Public Finance has also had several media campaigns to promote investment in government securities and the Romanian Government and the Bucharest Stock Exchange have promoted the listing of Hidroelectrica on the stock exchange. Various financial education books written by Romanian authors and adapted to the domestic economic context were also published. Global Money Week takes place from March 18 to 24, April 11 (every year) is Financial Education Day and October 31 has been designated World Saving Day. While not claiming to be an exhaustive inventory of financial education initiatives, it is clear that these kinds of initiatives have multiplied in recent years.

However, a recent study draws a bleak conclusion: "92% of the Romanian population is financially illiterate. The percentage rises to around 95% when measuring knowledge about the performance and risk of financial instruments" (Nițoi et al. 2022). The figures are worrisome especially if we take into account that "as more and more households are asked to make their own decisions on financial matters, financial illiteracy may become a serious threat to their lifetime well-being" (Batsaikhan & Demertzis, 2018). Financial literacy varies directly proportional to financial well-being and inversely proportional to the risk of poverty concluding that "in general, people with high levels of financial literacy also have an above average financial well-being index" (Nițoi et al. 2022) and that younger people have higher financial literacy compared to older people (Nițoi et al. 2022). Thus, the relationship between financial literacy and financial inclusion is one of interdependence: financial literacy contributes to increased access to financial services, and research findings have shown that bank account holders are more likely to be financially literate

and to use related financial services" (Nițoi et al. 2022). So the first step to reduce the risk of poverty, would be financial literacy which can be defined as "the process by which financial consumers/investors improve their understanding of financial products and concepts and, through information, instructions and/or objectives, advice, develop the skills and confidence to become more aware of financial risks and opportunities, make informed choices, know where to turn for help, and make effective decisions to improve their financial well-being" (OECD, 2005).

Unfortunately, our country is facing two situations that call into question the real possibilities of increasing financial literacy and financial education. The first aspect to be mentioned is the reluctance of the population, with 39% of the participants in a survey stating that they "are not interested in receiving information about financial concepts". This reluctance is also reflected in the choice of sources of information, with the majority of respondents turning to "personal experience and knowledge (41%) as the main source of information to inform financial decisions" (Nițoi et al. 2022). On the other hand, according to other studies, "48% of Romanians rely on their family and friends when they want advice on savings and investments, and 19% even on information from social media" (Erste Group, 2022). Moreover, "58% of respondents admit that they have not had access to financial information or interest to improve their financial literacy" (Unlock Market Research, 2021).

This reluctance could have multiple causes, but we cannot ignore the lack of trust in financial institutions. It was also fueled by the evolution of the financial market in Romania after the Revolution. Private banks appeared immediately after the fall of communism, but many of them went bankrupt, harming millions of citizens: Banca de Credit, Banca Columna, Banca Albina, Bankoop, Banca Internațională a Religiiilor, Banca Dacia Felix, Banca Română de Investiții, Banca Română de Comerț Exterior (Bancorex). Romania's accession to the European Union brought more stability to the financial market by regulating the financial sector and strengthening banking institutions. However, there have been several other situations that have affected Romanians' confidence in banks, such as the easing of credit conditions in 2006-2008 ("credit only with ID"), loans in Swiss francs and the 2008 real estate crisis. Although the financial-banking market is now regulated and banks are more solid, there are still a number of non-banking financial institutions (NFIs) that charge huge interest rates.

Despite the population's reluctance to financial education and lack of trust in banks, many Romanians believe that the most appropriate institutions are commercial banks, insurance companies, pension and investment funds, regulatory and consumer protection authorities and academia" (Nițoi et al. 2022). Another survey concludes that "61% of respondents believe that financial education is the responsibility of schools and other educational institutions, 56% believe it is the responsibility of parents and the family, and 45% place it on banks and other financial institutions" (Erste Group, 2022).

The second situation that diminishes the success of financial education initiatives (along with the reluctance of the population) is the very efficiency and effectiveness of these initiatives, in which case, the opinions of researchers are divergent. With regard to the efficiency and effectiveness of these initiatives, researchers' opinions diverge. On the one hand, an inventory of 76 experiments conducted on a sample of about 160,000 individuals concludes that, on average, financial education programs have a positive impact on both financial knowledge and behaviors (Kaiser et al. 2022). On the other hand,

another study that surveyed 168 papers in which the results of 201 previous studies were presented caught our attention. According to (Fernandes et al. 2014) efforts to enhance financial literacy account for only 0.1% of the variation in the financial behaviors examined, with even smaller effects observed in low-income groups. So it is not enough just to roll out these one-off initiatives; more is needed. The aforementioned authors draw an even more ominous conclusion: "like other education, financial education deteriorates over time; even large interventions with many hours of instruction have negligible effects on behavior 20 months or more after the intervention" (Fernandes et al. 2014). Unfortunately, this view is not singular, with other researchers reaching a similar conclusion." Follow-up of students who have taken such a course over a five-year period shows no positive impact on financial literacy, attitudes towards saving, or any favorable behavioral change" (Mandell, 2011). That the results of mass financial education are not as expected is also noted by Björklund and Sandahl in a recent paper (Björklund & Sandahl, 2023). The implications of these findings are that "52% of consumers tend to opt for the first product they see when they get a current bank account or credit card" (Jana, 2015).

The results of this study also reveal significant gaps in financial literacy and financial inclusion in Romania. Data suggest that despite national efforts, financial literacy rates remain low, particularly among the rural and older population. According to the World Bank (2021), access to financial services in rural areas is limited, which exacerbates the financial literacy gap. In addition, a study by Nițoi et al. (2022) indicates that Romania ranks low in financial literacy, with only a small share of the population showing a solid understanding of basic financial concepts.

The urban-rural gap continues to challenge financial inclusion efforts. As noted by OECD (2020), rural communities are often left behind in terms of access to educational resources, including financial education. This lack of access translates into fewer opportunities for people in these areas to acquire the knowledge necessary to engage in financial planning and the use of financial products. The digital transformation of the banking sector also plays an important role, as people who lack digital skills cannot fully benefit from online financial services (Atkinson & Messy, 2013). This digital divide further exacerbates the exclusion of these vulnerable populations.

Moreover, levels of financial literacy have a direct correlation with financial well-being. Research by Lusardi and Mitchell (2014) shows that individuals with greater financial literacy are more likely to participate in long-term financial planning, save regularly, and avoid high-interest loans. In the Romanian context, low literacy rates can increase susceptibility to financial instability, particularly in economically disadvantaged areas. By improving financial literacy, there is potential for wider economic benefits as more citizens become able to make informed financial decisions, contributing to greater economic stability.

Romania's initiatives in the area of financial education, such as the integration of financial education into the national school curriculum, reflect a growing awareness of the need for early intervention. However, the effectiveness of these programs remains limited due to a lack of consistent follow-up and practical application beyond the classroom. Research by Willis (2011) suggests that while financial education can improve knowledge, it does not always translate into better financial behaviors. Therefore, Romania must not only educate its citizens, but also create environments in which the behaviors learned can

be put into practice, particularly in controlled real-world scenarios such as simulations or community financial counseling.

Collaboration among stakeholders, including government institutions, banks, and non-governmental organizations, is critical to the success of financial education programs. Although various stakeholders in Romania have shown interest in improving financial education, their efforts remain fragmented. A coordinated approach, as recommended by Atkinson and Messy (2013), would help to unify these efforts into a comprehensive national strategy that targets all demographics, especially vulnerable groups such as low-income households and the elderly. By promoting partnerships between key players in the financial sector, educational institutions and community-based organizations, Romania can develop more effective and scalable financial education programs.

Increasing the effectiveness of financial education programs requires "designing instructional approaches that more effectively lead young people to put relevant financial knowledge into practice and to do so correctly when making financial decisions" (Salas-Velasco et al. 2021). Thus, there is a need to shift from an information-focused approach to a goal-focused, action-oriented and behavior change-oriented approach. If we refer to pupils and students, specific financial education concepts could also be included in the curriculum of other subjects (e.g. calculating interest and taxes in mathematics) and, depending on the age specificity of the learners, different stories or games could be used (Drăghici, 2024).

For high school students simulating scholarship activity through play "consistently increases literacy scores, indicating that teaching should be interactive, contemporary, and fun" (Mandell, 2011). It is also important to measure the effectiveness of these initiatives both in the short term (after the completion of the process) and in the medium term (six months and one year, respectively) after the initiative is completed.

Some researchers have realized that it is important to first educate teachers "about their own personal finances in order to better prepare them to teach financial education" (Hensley et al. 2017), and in Romania there is already since 2021 a course on "Economic and Financial Education for Teachers" accredited by the Ministry of Education and Research, the National Bank of Romania, the Romanian Banking Association, the Romanian Banking Institute, the Romanian Banking Institute, the Financial Supervisory Authority and the Institute of Financial Studies. "The target group of this course is secondary school teaching staff who teach the subject "Social Education" to 8th grade students" (M.E.C, 2021). This would have long-term implications both for individuals and for the economy in general because studies conclude that "an adequate level of basic financial literacy of the population contributes to individual well-being, to the stability of financial markets and to the smooth functioning of the economy" (Clichici & Moagăr-Poladian, 2022).

Although, as stated earlier, financial education should be primarily the responsibility of the individual, it is of real benefit to have financial education strategies at the national level. Their aim is to "improve people's ability to better manage (administer) their personal finances and to avoid or at least lessen financial stress and the severity of financial crises at the individual and family level" (Romanian Government, 2023).

As noted by other researchers, "the current institutional context is conducive to the implementation of financial education projects, given the increase in initiatives to strengthen the education sector and the existence of an initiative to implement a national strategy for financial education" (Nițoi et al. 2022). It only remains that, under the

coordination of the authorities (whether the Ministry of Education and Research, the National Bank of Romania, the Financial Supervisory Authority or any other institution), these projects should pursue a common goal and quantifiable objectives. In the near future, as far as financial education is concerned, the focus should shift from "what and how much is done" to "how" and, above all, "why" it is done. There is no doubt that the responsibility for financial education (as in any field) lies primarily with each individual. But if the individual is unwilling, unable or unable to educate himself or herself in financial matters, the state and public or private financial institutions should take responsibility for this. This study makes several original contributions to the specialized scientific literature by providing an integrated analysis of financial literacy, financial education, and financial inclusion in Romania. Unlike previous studies that address these topics separately, our research establishes a direct connection between financial literacy levels and financial inclusion, emphasizing the role of digital banking as a key enabler, particularly for vulnerable groups such as rural and elderly populations. Furthermore, by evaluating national financial education initiatives using institutional reports and secondary data, this study identifies both progress and persistent challenges, contributing to a more comprehensive understanding of the effectiveness of financial education programs.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, the results highlight the importance of a comprehensive and inclusive approach to financial education in Romania. This study contributes to the specialized scientific literature by providing a novel perspective on the interplay between financial literacy, digital banking, and financial inclusion in Romania. While progress has been made, significant challenges remain, particularly in reaching rural and elderly populations. To improve financial inclusion, Romania needs to focus on integrating digital literacy into financial education, improving the accessibility of programs and ensuring collaboration between stakeholders to create a solid financial education framework.

A number of measures need to be taken on the way financial education is taught at both secondary and high school levels and the way teachers are trained to teach the subject. In addition, companies should be more involved in running financial education programs for employees, as ensuring proper management of personal finances leads to happier and more productive employees.

This article contributes to the existing literature by offering a focused analysis of the interplay between financial literacy, education, and inclusion in Romania, with an emphasis on digital banking. It highlights the limitations of current programs and proposes a more integrated, collaborative approach to improve financial literacy and inclusion.

The article's limitations include its reliance on secondary data, which may not fully capture recent developments in financial literacy and digital banking. Additionally, it lacks empirical research, such as surveys or interviews, which could provide deeper insights into individual experiences and attitudes toward financial education and digital inclusion in Romania.

Taking in consideration that were not made studies on the subject for mountain region in Romania, we consider that future research should focus on conducting empirical studies, such as surveys and interviews, to assess the impact of financial education and digital banking initiatives, especially in this area. This region often face unique challenges,

including limited access to banking services and lower financial literacy rates. Investigating the specific needs of these communities will provide valuable insights for developing tailored strategies to improve financial inclusion and digital literacy in this underserved area.

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